

1 A NES interaction network.

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7 We hypothesize nestin has a central role in shaping invasive and migratory behaviors of the cancer cell.
8 We combined transcriptomic, proteomic and loss and gain-of-function genetics approaches to discovery of
9 molecules that interact with Nestin and exert NES function in cells.

10 Citations

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1. Nestin interacts with vimentin (VIM).
2. Nestin interacts with GFAP.
3. Nestin interacts with the neuroepithelial filaments NEFM and NEFL.
4. Nestin interacts with CDK5.
5. Nestin interacts with Myc.
6. Nestin interacts with Fam167a.
7. Nestin interacts with keratins KRT18, KRT31, and KRT8.
8. Nestin interacts with myogenic factor 6, Myf6 (herculin).
9. Nestin interacts with myogenic factor 4, myogenin.
10. Nestin binds tubulins Tuba1a and Tubb2a.